

Influence of pyrolysis variables on heating value of biochar from *Cortaderia Selloana*

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Keywords: *Cortaderia Selloana*; High Heating Value; Pyrolysis; Biochar

Abstract

Cortaderia Selloana (Schult. & Schult. f.) Asch. & Graebn, commonly known as pampas grass, is an invasive plant native to South America that proliferates in marginal areas, riverbanks, industrial land, road edges, and other locations worldwide [1]. In Cantabria (northern Spain), initial attempts to control its spread through cutting proved ineffective due to the species' adaptability, vigor, and high reproductive efficiency. The substantial costs associated with these control measures led to the abandonment of this strategy, resulting in the widespread propagation of pampas grass throughout the region. This article explores pathways for utilizing the waste generated by the invasive species *Cortaderia Selloana* (pampas grass) as a raw material for bioenergy production. Pyrolysis is considered the most cost-effective and straightforward method for transforming primary biomass into higher-value-added products. It is deemed emission-neutral and has gained importance in recent years due to its ability to extract high energy value from biomass while reducing its volume, thus positively impacting environmental costs. The quality of the biochar produced depends on various factors, including the parent biomass, pyrolysis temperature, heating rate, residence time, and particle size [2, 3]. The objective was to determine how operational variables controlling the pyrolysis process (temperature, nitrogen flow, and particle size) affect the High Heating Value (HHV) of the resulting biochar. The study utilized 6-gram samples in a vertically inserted quartz fixed-bed reactor measuring 360 mm in length and 26 mm in inner diameter. The reactor was positioned in an electric oven. Response Surface Methodology (RSM) was employed using a rotatable central composite design to investigate the influence of these factors on the HHV response. This approach enables the manipulation of operational variables to maximize the HHV of the resulting biochar. The factors of pyrolysis temperature and particle size were found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) in determining the HHV of the biochar, while nitrogen flow was not. The HHV ranged from 27.54 to 24.00 MJ kg⁻¹. Analysis of the developed mathematical model suggests that smaller particle sizes and higher pyrolysis temperatures lead to higher HHV values for the biochar. The valorization of waste from this invasive species through pyrolysis is expected to contribute to a more economically sustainable control strategy.

References

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Acknowledgements - This work was supported by the Government of Cantabria, “Bridge Projects 2023” (Development of forestry bioeconomy through microwave-assisted stepwise pyrolysis, PID2022-138142OB-I00), Solvay, under projects 3399 and 3824 and EUROPEAN COMMISSION, Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions—RISE, grant number 101007733 (CELISE project).